

ON THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN FATIGUE CRACK GROWTH AND FRACTURE RESISTANCE CURVE IN CERAMICS

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ABSTRACT

Fatigue crack growth and fracture resistance curve (R -curve) were investigated in a silicon carbide whisker reinforced alumina composite ($\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-SiC}_w$), a polycrystalline alumina (AD90) and a gas pressure sintered silicon nitride (EC-141) at room temperature in air using a combined loading technique for stabilizing crack growth and a surface film technique for monitoring crack length. Based on the experimental results, the relationship between the fatigue crack growth and the R -curve was discussed, and the significance of the threshold stress intensity factor, K_{th} as a material parameter was suggested.

Keywords: fatigue crack growth, fracture resistance curve, fracture toughness, wake effect, composite ceramics, monolithic ceramics.

1. INTRODUCTION

The authors have investigated fatigue crack growth (FCG), fracture toughness (K_{Ic}) and fracture resistance curve (R -curve) of ceramics at room temperature in air [1, 2]. The results indicated that crack growth behavior was dominated by shielding effects in the wake region of crack tip and cyclic loading caused fretting damage resulted in the reduction of the shielding effects. Therefore, FCG rate, da/dN , was determined by the reduction rate of the shielding effects [1-3].

In metallic systems, the dominating mechanism of FCG, K_{Ic} and R -curve is basically crack tip plasticity. Fracture mechanics presents geometrically independent evaluation which is important to assess the fracture of structures and components. The data on FCG are used for the basis of damage tolerant design, in which the K_{Ic} and the R -curve are regarded as the upper limit of crack driving force for stable fatigue crack growth [4]. In order to establish the practical usage of the fracture mechanics data on FCG, K_{Ic} and R -curve in ceramics, it is necessary to clarify the correlations among those crack growth characteristics.

From this point of view, FCG and R -curve were investigated in a silicon carbide whisker reinforced alumina composite ($\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-SiC}_w$), a polycrystalline alumina (AD90) and a gas pressure sintered silicon nitride (EC-141) at room temperature in air, using a combined loading technique for stabilizing crack growth and a surface film technique for monitoring crack length. Based on these experimental results, the correlations among the K_{Ic} , R -curve and FCG characteristics are discussed.

2. MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

$\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-SiC}_w$ was supplied by Kawasaki Steel Co. The diameter and length of SiC whisker were $1.85\ \mu\text{m}$ and $10\text{--}100\ \mu\text{m}$, respectively. The volume fraction of SiC whisker was 20%. The mechanical properties were: flexural strength, $\sigma_F = 561\ \text{MPa}$ and fracture toughness, $K_{Ic} = 5.0\ \text{MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$ (IF method) [5]. AD90 was commercially available from Coors Ceramics Co. The purity of alumina was 90%. The grain size was between 2 and $10\ \mu\text{m}$ with the average value of $4\ \mu\text{m}$. The mechanical properties were: tensile strength, $\sigma_B = 221\ \text{MPa}$, compressive strength, $\sigma_c = 2482\ \text{MPa}$, $\sigma_F = 338\ \text{MPa}$ and Young's modulus, $E = 276\ \text{GPa}$. EC-141 was also commercially available from NGK Spark Plug Co. The mechanical properties in the catalogue were: $\sigma_F = 900\ \text{MPa}$, $E = 320\ \text{GPa}$, Vickers hardness, $H_v = 14.3\ \text{GPa}$, $K_{Ic} = 6.0\ \text{MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$ (SEPB method) [6].

Experiments were performed in a computer-controlled oil hydraulic testing machine with a load capacity of 4.9 kN. Specimens used were of compact type with width, $W = 25\ \text{mm}$, thickness, $B = 5\ \text{mm}$, height, $H = 30\ \text{mm}$ and notch length, $a_n = 9\ \text{mm}$. Crack length was measured continuously by the surface film technique [7], in which changes in crack length were monitored by a thin layer of Pt-Pd deposited on the surface area encompassing the region of fracture. The propagation of a crack leads to a break in the Pt-Pd film which is atomically bonded to the surface of the specimen. The Pt-Pd layer is connected to an electrical circuit where an increase in crack length is reflected as a change in the electric resistance of the film. The calibration and evaluation of this technique were given in Ref. [7].

Stable FCG was evaluated successfully using a combined loading technique, in which a compressive load was applied to the uncracked ligament of compact specimens together with a cyclic tensile load applied at loading holes. The cyclic loading frequencies, f , were 1 and 10 Hz. The maximum stress intensity factor, K_{max} , in fatigue cycle was kept approximately constant under constant amplitude loading regardless of crack growth. Stress intensity factor, K , under the combined loading condition was given in Ref. [1].

Load shedding fatigue crack growth tests were performed until crack became dormant, in order to determine the threshold stress intensity factor, K_{th} . Subsequently, the specimens were used for the quasi-static tests under monotonic loading condition at a displacement rate of $2.5\ \mu\text{m}/\text{min}$ without the compressive load applied to the ligament. The R -curves and critical K values for stable crack growth were determined in this experiment.

3. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

3.1. Fatigue crack growth

Figure 1 shows the relationship between crack extension Δa and number of cycles N for $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-SiC}_w$ obtained in the FCG test under $K_{\text{max}} = 6.1\ \text{MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$. The crack initiated at N

Figure 1. Relationship between Δa and N in $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-SiC}_w$.

$= 0.7 \times 10^4$ and grew very slowly. Subsequently, the crack growth was accelerated at $N = 1.2 \times 10^4$ until Δa achieved 0.1 mm followed by a slow crack growth. Similar fluctuations in crack growth rate were seen in this material under all loading conditions.

Figure 2 shows the fracture surface of FCG region in $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-SiC}_w$. Secondary cracks were observed between whiskers. Based on the SEM observation, the mechanism of FCG is demonstrated in Fig. 3 in conjunction with the schematic illustration of the fluctuation in FCG rate. In stage A, microcracks are generated between whiskers in the matrix in front of the main crack. The microcrack generation leads to the slow increase in electric resistance of the surface film which results in the slow increase in Δa . When the microcrack density increases to a certain level, the main crack traces some of the microcracks. This behavior is detected as the rapid increase in Δa . Fracture surface of FCG region was rougher than that of fast fracture region. The crack growth model in Fig. 3 can explain the increased roughness of FCG region.

Figures 4 and 5 show the relationships between Δa and N in EC-141 and AD90, respectively. The FCG characteristics in EC-141 were similar to those in $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-SiC}_w$. The microstructure

Figure 2. Fracture surface of FCG region in $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-SiC}_w$ showing that secondary cracks were initiated between whiskers.

Figure 3. Schematic illustration of crack growth mechanism in $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-SiC}_w$.

of EC-141 was composed of glassy phase in the grain boundary and β long grain with diameter of $0.8 \sim 1 \mu\text{m}$ and aspect ratio of $2 \sim 8$ [6, 8]. The β long grains are considered to play similar role in mechanical behavior during the fracture process to SiC whisker for $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-SiC}_w$. Thus, the crack growth characteristics and fracture mechanisms become similar in these materials. On the other hand, FCG in AD90 was discontinuous including arrest and abrupt growth. This growth behavior was similar to that in a polycrystalline magnesia presented in previous work [1, 2].

Paris plots derived from the FCG experiments are presented in Fig. 6(a) for AD90 and $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-SiC}_w$. The arrests and the fluctuations of the crack growth were ignored and the da/dN values were obtained from the averages under constant K_{max} conditions. It is clear that the effect of loading frequency is negligible in both materials. The power law relationship between da/dN and K_{max} is expressed as;

$$da/dN = C \cdot K_{\text{max}}^m \quad (1)$$

where m for AD90 and $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-SiC}_w$ were approximately 30 and 80, respectively.

Paris plots for EC-141 are presented in Fig. 6(b) together with data obtained by Sugawara et al. [9] using constant moment method [10]. The experiments were performed with and without using the combined loading technique, which are denoted by "Clamped" and "No

Figure 4. Relationship between Δa and N in EC-141.

Figure 5. Relationship between Δa and N in AD90.

(a) $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-SiC}_w$ and AD90

(b) EC-141

Figure 6. Paris plot of da/dN vs. K_{max} .

clamp”, respectively. The effect of loading frequency on the FCG is also negligible for this material. However, the relationships between da/dN and K_{max} are different in the tests with and without using the combined loading technique. Also, da/dN is much higher in the constant moment method than in the present results. These results indicate that the power law relationships between da/dN and K_{max} is dependent on the specimen geometry and loading systems. When K_{th} is defined as the K_{max} value corresponding to $da/dN = 1 \times 10^{-10}$ m/cycle determined by extrapolating the power law relationships, K_{th} is independent of the specimen geometry and loading systems, being approximately $4 \text{ MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$.

3.2. Fracture resistance curve

The specimens used for the FCG tests were loaded monotonically in order to determine the fracture resistance curve. Figure 7(a) shows the relationships between the applied K and Δa ($= a - a_0$), where a_0 is the crack length at which K_{th} has been achieved in the FCG tests. In the case of AD90, the electric resistance of the surface film decreased upon unloading because of crack closure and Δa was -0.52 mm under complete unloading condition. Subsequently, it increased rapidly as K increased due to crack opening. The Δa became zero at $K = 2.2 \text{ MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$, which agreed with the K_{th} value in the FCG test. However, Δa decreased to a negative value again with a further increase in K . This behavior indicates that the contact condition in the wake of the crack tip is changing and the crack is not fully open in this K region. The Δa began to increase stably at $K = 3.15 \text{ MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$ until the instability occurred at $\Delta a = 0.025 \text{ mm}$ and $K = 3.29 \text{ MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$.

In the case of $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-SiC}_w$, the decrease in Δa due to crack closure was not observed. However, Δa began to decrease to a negative value at $K = 5.90 \text{ MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$. Subsequently, stable crack growth started at $K = 6.52 \text{ MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$ until the instability occurred at $\Delta a = 0.145 \text{ mm}$ and $K = 6.88 \text{ MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$.

Figure 7(b) shows the result for EC-141 compared to that obtained by Maniette et al. [8] for the same material. The decrease in Δa before the stable crack growth was not observed. However, the crack growth behavior was similar to that of $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-SiC}_w$. In the experiment by Maniette et al., a compact specimen with $W = 15.6 \text{ mm}$ and $B = 0.9 \text{ mm}$ was used in conjunction with crack stabilizer [8]. The specimen was precracked with Δa of 3 mm from the notch root and then renotched the wake region of the precrack except the crack tip region with length of $10 \mu\text{m}$. They claimed that the shielding effect in the wake of the crack tip could be minimized with this precracking technique. The crack initiated at the K value of $4.3 \text{ MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$ which was much lower than that for the fatigue precrack obtained in the present investigation. Fracture resistance increases with the crack growth up to $6.5 \text{ MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$, at which the R -curve become flat. This K value agrees with that for instability point of the fatigue precracked specimen. Therefore, it is suggested that the shielding effect remains in the wake region of the fatigue precrack.

Figure 7 Fracture resistance curves.

4. DISCUSSION

The authors investigated the FCG and the R -curve in polycrystalline magnesia and demonstrated that the crack growth characteristics were controlled by the shielding effects in the wake of the crack tip [1, 2]. The shielding effects are reduced by cyclic loading which promotes fretting damage in the wake region [1-3, 11]. A schematic illustration of the relationship between FCG and R -curve in ceramics is given in Fig. 8(a), provided that the crack growth characteristics are dominated by the shielding effects in the wake of the crack tip under monotonic and cyclic loadings. In Fig. 8, K_{Ic} is the fracture toughness of an ideal crack, K_{sc} is the fracture toughness with maximum shielding effect, K_{th} is the threshold stress intensity factor for fatigue crack growth and K_{fc} is the fatigue fracture toughness at which FCG become unstable. Assuming that the shielding effects in the wake are completely eliminated by cyclic loading and that the fracture mechanism at the crack tip is the same under monotonic and cyclic loadings, K_{th} would represent the minimum fracture resistance, which corresponds to K_{Ic} . The values of K_{sc} and K_{fc} are considered to be identical, because both values represent the fracture resistance with the maximum shielding effects in the wake.

It has been recognized that fracture mechanisms under monotonic and cyclic loadings were the same except that there was a fretting damage in the stable FCG region for non-transforming ceramics [1-3, 9, 11]. Therefore, K_{th} value must be equal to K_{Ic} value if the shielding effects are completely eliminated by cyclic loads. As shown in Figures 6(b) and 7(b), it was demonstrated in EC-141 that the K_{th} and K_{Ic} values were approximately the same. However, Figure 7 suggested that there were shielding effects in fatigue precrack up to the K value at which the crack growth instability occurred. This behavior seems to contradict with the above discussion on the relationship between K_{th} and K_{Ic} , because the R -curves were determined with the specimens used for the FCG tests, in which K_{th} values were obtained. Detailed examination of the R -curve for AD90 shown in Fig. 7(a) gives the following explanation for the contradiction. The Δa value which was negative under unloading condition became zero when the applied K value attained $2.2 \text{ MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$. This K value was equal to the K_{th} value. Thus, the shielding effects were negligible at this value of K . However, Δa became negative again with increasing K above K_{th} and the shielding effects began to work again. This

Figure 8. Relationships between R -curve and FCG.

complicated behavior suggests that the shielding effect under monotonic loading is different from that under cyclic loading.

The relationship between R -curve and FCG for metallic systems is illustrated in Fig. 8(b). The upper limit of the stable fatigue crack growth is determined by K_{Ic} and/or R -curve [4], and the value of K_{th} is much smaller than that of K_{Ic} . The region of stage II fatigue crack growth, in which damage tolerant design is established, corresponds to the blunting process of a crack under monotonic loading. The crack growth characteristic in this region is stable and independent of specimen geometry. In ceramic systems, on the other hand, K levels for fatigue crack growth and R -curve are approximately the same, and their growth mechanisms are basically similar. It has been clarified that R -curve depended strongly on specimen geometry, i.e. crack length [12], size [13] and etc., and that FCG rates also depended on specimen geometry [14]. Therefore, the characteristics of these crack growths are not important as a material property, and it is suggested that K_{Ic} which represents the minimum crack growth resistance is the most important material parameter for fracture mechanics evaluation in ceramics. However, the values of fracture toughness obtained by the conventional techniques evaluate the instability point on the R -curve, which corresponds to K_{sc} value in Fig. 8(a), and there is no simple technique to determine the accurate K_{Ic} value. Since the values of K_{th} and K_{Ic} are equal provided that the shielding effects in the wake are completely eliminated by cyclic loads, it can be proposed that the K_{th} should be used in place of the K_{Ic} for fracture mechanics evaluation.

5. CONCLUSIONS

Fatigue crack growth and fracture resistance curve (R -curve) were investigated in a silicon carbide whisker reinforced alumina composite ($Al_2O_3-SiC_w$), a polycrystalline alumina (AD90) and a gas pressure sintered silicon nitride (EC-141) at room temperature in air. The following conclusions can be made.

1. Fatigue crack growth was evaluated successfully for the materials using the present experimental techniques. The crack growth was continuous with fluctuations in $Al_2O_3-SiC_w$ and EC-141, while the discontinuous growth was observed in AD90. This difference in crack growth behavior was attributed to the crack growth mechanisms for the materials.
2. R -curves were evaluated under monotonic loading for the specimens with which K_{th} had been determined in FCG tests. Measured R -curves did not increase markedly with crack growth. The R -curve was different from that for an ideal crack, because of the shielding effects in the wake region of the fatigue precracked specimens.
3. Based on the experimental results, the significance of K_{th} as a material parameter was pointed out.

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